

THE ANALYSIS OF USING BISOPROLOL IN PATIENTS WITH MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

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Purpose: To assess the frequency of use for the treatment cardioselective β 1-blocker bisoprolol for patients with myocardial infarction (SMI). **Material and methods:** Analysis was conducted of medical records (medical history) of 65 patients with SMI. Of these 48 (73.8%) were men and 17 (26.2%) women. Heart rate in men was - from 60 to 110 per minute, the average heart rate - 85 ± 13.8 min. Heart rate in women was - from 64 to 115 per minute, the average heart rate - 90 ± 12.6 min. All cases to use of bisoprolol in these patients were analyzed. In the treatment of patients with SMI, only 23 patients were treated with bisoprolol, which amounted to 35.4%. In 23 (35.4%) of the patients diagnosed the 2 type of diabetes, they did not receive this drug. In 43 (66.2%) patients had chronic heart failure (CHF), 6 of them (9.2%) I stage, 24 (36.9%) - CHF II A, 13 (20%) - CHF II B. In patients with CHF I only received 4 bisoprolol in a daily dose of 2.5 - 5 mg, with CHF II A only 12 received bisoprolol in a daily dose of 5 mg. Among patients with CHF II B drug is not appointed. **Results:** The main reason for the insufficient use of β adrenoblocker are unjustified fear of development to side effects. Often the reason for non-use of β - blockers is the presence of accompany diseases. As expected, the frequency of the destination β - blockers was lower in elderly patients, patients with diabetes and heart failure. It is justified because β - blockers may exacerbate hypoglycemia condition and neutralize its clinical manifestations. On the other hand the use of bisoprolol in patients with diabetes more effectively prevents the development of re-infarction and sudden death than patients without diabetes. Bisoprolol devoid of adverse metabolic effects of nonselective β - blockers, as hypoglycemia, hypoxalemia, increased levels of very low density lipoprotein and plasma triglycerides. **Conclusion:** Thus in the clinical practice of the - for the continued cautious position of doctors to beta. - blockers modern and more effective drugs are used less frequently than necessary. Moreover, the frequency of their use becomes particularly low was in the groups of patients with high risk of complications - ischemic heart disease, hypertension, diabetes. This is due to the reevaluation of contraindications, the risk of developing side effects and a lack of knowledge about the benefits of β - blockers than with other drugs.

THE MODERN APPROACH OF DIAGNOSIS OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE

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Objective: Identification of risk groups by gender, age, the study of the characteristic changes of the electrocardiogram, chest radiograph, spirometry and laboratory changes in COPD. **Methods:** The history of the disease, the general analysis of blood, electrocardiography, chest radiography, spirometry and a peak-flow monitoring. **Results:** The study of 104 people who were hospitalized in the Municipal medical association in the Department of Pulmonology and Allergology. Out of 104 male patients 56 (53.8%), 48 women (46.2%). The average age of men is 52 years old, women 52.9 years. Accompanying disease are found in 48.9% of cases: Ischemic heart disease, angina, hypertension, rheumatism, diabetes, tuberculosis. At 29.5 % patients hemoglobin of less than 100g / l, leukocytosis - in 10.2% of cases, increasing erythrocyte sedimentation rate in 44.3% of cases. Changes in the electrocardiogram have been observed in 68.2% of cases, among them: blockade of the left leg bundle of His and branches, hypertrophy of the right and left ventricles, disturbance of intraventricular conduction, hypertrophy of the right atrium with the overload, polipronye and atrial arrhythmia, myocardial hypoxia, ischemia phenomenon, tachycardia, atrial fibrillation, in severe cases, the phenomenon of chronic pulmonary heart disease (10.2%). Radiographic changes were observed in 53.4% of cases, among which 48% phenomenon chronic bronchitis; 21% of emphysema; 31% - a combination of pneumosclerosis and fibrosis. Also observed pleurisy, single or double-sided pneumonia. Indicators spirometry and pikuometrii determined a violation of respiratory function on the mixed type with a predominance of obstruction. **Conclusion:** The results show that COPD often suffer from men, that younger than 50 years. Almost 50 percent of cases the disease occurs on the background of comorbidity. Predominantly affects the respiratory and cardiovascular system. It should be noted that the disease progresses steadily and results in disablement. Therefore, you must timely early diagnosis and timely treatment of the disease in patients with COPD prolong the life of patients with COPD.

DETERMINATION OF RISK GROUPS IN LIVER CIRRHOSIS

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Relevance. Liver cirrhosis - chronic liver disease, which is a consequence of the formation of multiple scars. The main causes of cirrhosis are alcohol abuse and chronic hepatitis. **Objective:** Identify the prevalence rate of patients with liver cirrhosis, certain risk groups by age and gender, clinical features of the disease, according to the Samarkand City Medical Association. **Methods:** As material investigated 88 patients who are hospitalized in the period from December, 2015 to February, 2016 in the gastroenterology department. The main method of research is the study of history, as well as: a general analysis of blood, biochemical blood test, liver function tests (thymol), ECG study, determination of blood glucose. **Results:** Among them, 58 men (66%), 30 women (34%). The average age of women - 48.5 years, male 35.2. Accompanying disease occurs - in 62.5% of cases, including: coronary heart disease, hypertension, cholecystitis, chronic pancreatitis. In 49 patients for analysis of glucose, which is higher than normal blood in 13 (26.5%) was carried out (55.9%) which indicated a combination of cirrhosis with diabetes. Complications of liver cirrhosis in 49 patients (55.9%) proceeds as hepatocellular failure, portal hypertension, 42 (47.7%) - polideficiency anemia. In 8 of them (9%), biliary dyskinesia. ECG examination was performed in 63 (71.5%), identified the following changes: ischemic heart disease, atrial fibrillation, ventricular hypertrophy with both overload of them, left ventricular hypertrophy, and metabolic changes in myocardium, the blockade of the lower posterolateral branch of the left bundle branch block, myocardial hypoxia posterior wall the left ventricle. Thymol test in 53 patients (60%) - increased. The enzymes ALT, AST increased in 31 (35.2%). Increased bilirubin (direct, indirect) was observed in 39 (44.3%), erythrocyte sedimentation rate in 57 (64.7%). **Conclusion:** The process of liver destruction can be slowed down by a complex of therapeutic measures. Risk group consists of patients with chronic hepatitis and alcoholism. At the same time middle-aged men are suffered more often than women. A timely diagnosis and rational treatment prolong the patient's life and improve its quality.